

Dyes Derived from Thiohydantoin. Part I.

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It has been observed in this laboratory that the intensely coloured condensation products from thiohydantoin and aromatic aldehydes may be used for the dyeing of woolen and silk fabrics. In course of the present investigation, it has been found that thiohydantoin also condenses with aromatic nitroso- and isonitroso-compounds in presence of glacial acetic acid or acetic anhydride forming products (I) which are even more coloured than those obtained with aldehydes.

With acetic anhydride as the condensing agent, unstable acetyl derivatives, presumably of the type (II), are generally formed, which are however very easily hydrolysed by dilute alkalis (or by boiling water) to the free keto-types (I).

On account of the difficulty of purification of the acetyl derivatives due to their unstable nature, the condensation products described in this paper have been isolated only in the free keto-forms (I).

The condensation of thiohydantoin with isonitroso-compounds (like isonitrosocamphor, benzilmonoxime, etc.) may be explained by the assumption that these are at first converted into true nitroso-compounds by the migration of a hydrogen atom and then the condensation takes place in the usual manner.

If to the alcoholic solution of these dyestuffs a little caustic soda is added, the colour in many cases is considerably intensi-

fed. This behaviour is due to the possibility, which they possess, of passing into the quinonoid forms, thus:

In cases where the formation of the quinonoid structure is not possible, the colour change is not very marked, and there the enolisation may be supposed to take place as already explained.

The following nitroso- and isonitroso-compounds have been condensed with thiohydantoin, and the products isolated in pure form, and described in the experimental portion in the same order: (1) nitrosobenzene, (2) *p*-nitrosophenol, (3) nitroso- β -naphthol, (4) nitrosothymol, (5) nitrosoresorcinol, (6) *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline, (7) *p*-nitrosodiethylaniline, (8) phenylmethylnitrosamine, (9) phenylethyl-nitrosamine, (10) nitrosodiphenylamine, (11) nitrosophenyl- α -naphthylamine, (12) nitrosophenyl- β -naphthylamine, (13) nitrosomethyl- β -naphthylamine, (14) nitrosocarbazole, (15) nitrosodimethyl-*m*-amidophenol, (16) nitrosodiethyl-*m*-amidophenol, (17) nitrosophenylhydroxylamine, (18) isonitrosocamphor, (19) isonitroso-1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone, (20) violuric acid, (21) benzilmonoxime and (22) phenanthraquinonemonoxime. Unsuccessful attempts were also made to condense the following aliphatic nitroso- and isonitroso-compounds with thiohydantoin: nitrosomethylurethane, *ter*.-nitrosobutane and isonitrosomethylethylketone. From this it seems that aliphatic compounds do not take part in the reaction. Most of the condensation products that have been isolated are crystalline substances, and they dye beautiful shades on wool and silk from a bath rendered slightly alkaline with borax or ammonium carbonate. They also dye cotton from a soda-bath (2% Na₂CO₃) in shades which are somewhat weaker than in the preceding cases.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Phenyliminothiohydantoin.—A mixture of thiohydantoin (2.5 g.), nitrosobenzene (2.2 g.) and acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) was heated under reflux on a sand-bath for 45 minutes. The reaction which was very vigorous at first, gradually subsided, and it was complete when the original dark green solution finally assumed a deep brownish-yellow shade. The mixture was allowed to cool and then

poured into water, when a brown precipitate came down. This was filtered off, washed with hot water, dissolved in warm dilute caustic soda and reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid. Finally it was crystallised from alcohol in fine stout prisms with a nut-brown colour.

Condensations of thiohydantoin with the rest of the nitroso- and isonitroso-compounds were similarly carried out with only slight modifications to suit individual cases. For the sake of abbreviation the properties of these compounds have been summarised in tabular form.

